

Behind the Lens: The Drawbacks of Media Exposure to Young Children's Social Development

Sophia Avrill J. Celada¹, Marbhie James A. Grafilo², Angela Cabriel G. Japay³, Farrah Faye C. Yamas⁴, Genesis G. Genelza*⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} University of Mindanao Tagum College, Philippines

Basic Education – Junior High School Department

ABSTRACT: Media exposure to young children is concerning in today's digital age. Although children can learn from media, excessive exposure can have alarming consequences. This systematic literature review aimed to determine the drawbacks of media exposure to young children's social development. The review attained four thematic points: Having Poor Sleeping Habits, Dealing with Aggressive Behaviors and Social Isolation, Interfering with Social Skills Development and Emotional Regulation, and Distorting Reality Perception and Weakening Attention Span through Media Sensationalism. Early media exposure to young children is one of the main reasons why there are negative impacts on children's overall well-being. To address these issues, educators, parents, and guardians should promote proper handling and monitoring of children's media access so that families can identify their child's behavior and how to mitigate this pressing issue. The media may affect the children in the long run as it can also affect their academic performance. Hence, it is not a platform for children; they should not be exposed to any media platforms at an early age.

Corresponding Author:

Genesis G. Genelza

Orcid: 0000-0001-5577-7480

KEYWORDS:

Media Exposure, Philippine Review, Social Development, Young Children.

INTRODUCTION

As the world adapts to social media, excessive screen time has increased, particularly during the worldwide pandemic when governments mandated that everyone, especially children, stay home. Nowadays, more children than before have been exposed to media for a long time at extremely young ages because of media gadgets; 90% of kids are under two years old. Media exposure can result in the loss of time for creative play and parental interaction, which are essential for children's social development (Kim et al., 2023). Media gadgets are convenient for enabling communication and performing specific ordinary chores; it is nearly hard to resist utilizing them daily. The same goes for young children surrounded by displays with internet access (del Dujo et al., 2021).

In China, a survey conducted on 3 to 6-year-olds in 35 kindergartens resulted in 57.3% of the Children being exposed to digital screens on technological devices for over two hours per day. Because of too much media exposure in the early years of childhood, children's health is continuously affected, becoming a widespread occurrence enough to get our attention. Considering that most babies are now exposed to the media at such a young age, investigating the influence of media on children's continuous health development is reasonable (Liu et al., 2021).

Moreover, through years of online activity, the Philippines is one of the top media consumers in the world. It is stated in this study that the connection between screen usage and the psychological development of children is complicated and has both positive and negative results. Excessive use of devices by children has been linked to dangers for concentration problems, developmental delays, lower academic performance, eating cycles, and sleep cycles. Furthermore, there is evidence that extended screen time exposure is connected to the children's subsequent teenagers' lower quality of life and bad diets (Dy et al., 2023).

Additionally, this study is anchored on the Social Learning Theory of Bandura (1977), which explains how the media easily influences people. The theory predicts that children will pay attention and retain in memory the behavior and information they hear and see in media and that knowledge will be put directly into their behaviors. The theory also states that attention and retention are

the foundation of learning processes. Individuals whose influence is impactful are likely to attract observers' attention, who will serve as role models and be the ones they will imitate.

Also, Huesmann (1986) states that media consumption contributes to children's brains, mainly the child's behavior. It provides major foresight that early childhood exposure to violent television may be particularly significant to young children's development because young children lack knowledge of various kinds of social conflict or problem scenarios. As a result, they are less likely to have strategic minds than older kids.

Besides, the study is grounded in Astington, Harris, and Olson's (1988) theory, which states that children start comprehending the mental states of those around them when they are four. This theory suggests that children exposed to the media at an early age may also be influenced by dangerous or malicious actions displayed in the media. Children who are regularly exposed to media content may pick up possibly harmful behaviors like violence, deception, or risky activities along with prosocial and educational messages.

While global and national studies have thoroughly examined the disadvantages of media exposure to young children, there remains a significant gap in understanding the experiences of media exposure to young children, particularly to those whose health is affected by exposure to media at an early age, such as loss of time for creative play, loss of time for parental interaction, development delays, lower academic performance, eating cycles, and sleep cycle. This gap is crucial to address, as the impact of exposure to media on young children affects their development, resulting in the decline of their future.

Generally, the importance of this study lies in its potential to raise awareness among individuals, especially parents/guardians. By offering insightful data, this study enlightens and educates families facing difficulties with the development and well-being of their children exposed early to media. In addition, this study is essential for resolving the present issue and developing new strategies to support families worldwide. Thus, providing the necessary information to address the problem of the study will also benefit the researchers.

This study aligns with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3 - Good Health and Well-being and 4 - Quality Education, which aims to guarantee healthy lives at all ages and inclusive, equitable quality education promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all.

METHOD

Research Design

The study employed a systematic literature review (SLR) as a qualitative methodology to study the drawbacks of media exposure to young children's social development issues. The systematic literature review is an intentional process for finding, assessing, and summarizing prior research on a particular topic. To find all relevant research on the topic of interest, a thorough search is done across multiple databases, academic journals, and other sources. The systematic review's approach should be clearly stated, and the criteria should be fully specified before the investigation. Other researchers can replicate this thorough and transparent search by accessing various databases and grey literature sources. This entails developing a detailed search strategy and emphasizing finding answers to a particular problem (Dewey & Drahota, 2016).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following claims and reliable information based on the findings from the chosen papers were highlighted in this study, as shown in Table 1.

This review attained four thematic points about the drawbacks of media exposure to young children: *Having Poor Sleeping Habits, Dealing with Aggressive Behaviors and Social Isolation, Interfering with Social Skills Development and Emotional Regulation, and Distorting Reality Perception and Weakening Attention Span through Media Sensationalism*. Early media exposure to young children is one of the main reasons why there are negative impacts on children's overall well-being. Even though the media is beneficial for expanding their intellect, the effects of too much media exposure always fall short in the eyes of everyone, especially parents. Furthermore, young children are exposed to media because they are given early access to gadgets. The idea of each theme presented in this study has the potential to raise awareness among parents and young children.

Having Poor Sleeping Habits

The first theme generated during the data gathering is that media exposure to Young Children leads to poor sleeping habits. This means that media can affect a child's sleeping habits and may lead to sleep deprivation. This is because the media, especially

for children, is very addictive. The media is an open platform; anything can be uploaded, including inappropriate content children may view. Viewing inappropriate content will negatively affect the children's psychological and mental health, leading to an unhealthy sleep habit.

Moreover, the study of Lin et al. (2022) showed that most toddlers in mainland China did not meet the World Health Organization's (WHO) screen time guidelines. Infants and toddlers who spent more time on screens slept less at night. The study emphasized that early childhood screen time can interfere with the development of regular sleep habits, which could result in long-term behavioral and cognitive problems. It also highlighted how crucial it is to restrict screen usage in the early years of childhood development in order to improve sleep quality and general well-being.

Chandranaik et al. (2024) also supported the theme, stating that most children have poor sleeping habits, with digital media use prevalent. Approximately 30 minutes of digital media before bed is associated with poor sleeping habits. The natural sleep-wake cycle is disturbed when excessive screen time and media exposure before bed are combined. This can lead to sleep deprivation and other negative effects that significantly impact children's health and development, thereby impeding the learning process (Genelza, 2024).

With this, it is essential not to undervalue the influence that media consumption has on kids' sleeping patterns. The media can greatly influence children's sleep patterns if not well observed. To prevent excessive screen time from endangering children's mental, psychological, and physical health, parents must play a crucial role in monitoring and directing children's media usage.

Dealing with Aggressive Behaviors and Social Isolation

The second theme developed during data gathering is that young children's media exposure resulted in dealing with aggressive behaviors and social isolation. This explains that media exposure influences the child's emotional, social, and developmental growth, where a child shows aggressiveness, such as hitting, yelling, and other disruptive behavior, and isolates themselves from social events. Technology has advanced so much recently that even screen-based content has been rising yearly. This means that young children are becoming more exposed to the media than before.

Furthermore, this was supported by Kumar et al. (2023), who stated that excessive screen time usage can positively and negatively impact children's development. However, their study results show that excessive screen time usage can negatively affect children's development, impair their comprehension and aggressive behavior, and hinder social and emotional competence. This means that early media exposure to young children greatly impacts their lives as they grow.

In addition, Coutinho et al. (2020) examined how children with neurodevelopmental diagnoses had been exposed to and had access to mobile devices. They also examined the social and emotional consequences of this with interaction, particularly in the context of social isolation. With the rise of media gadgets, parents often turn to these devices to keep their children occupied, especially in busy moments. This makes it difficult for young children to develop social skills, and it can lead to a preference for virtual communication rather than face-to-face interactions.

Hence, early media exposure to young children significantly impacts many aspects of young children's healthy development, leading to problems such as aggressive behavior and social isolation. As the child grows, their life will get harder to manage if they are too much exposed to the media. Therefore, controlling media exposure is essential to ensure the children's healthier growth development and social skills.

Interfering with Social Skills Development and Emotional Regulation

The third theme analyzed during the data gathering is that media exposure to young children interferes with their social skills development and emotional regulation. This hypothesized that media exposure can also affect the children's social skills development and emotional regulation, wherein the child limits real-world social interaction and struggles to manage their emotions healthily. At such a critical stage of development, their relationship with media exposure has begun to increase; this means that too much exposure to media can affect the child's overall well-being as they grow.

Moreover, this was supported by Kim, MD et al. (2023), that if the children are exposed to the media at an early age, they lose the time to interact with their parents and cannot play creatively, which can hurt social development. Excessive screen time can limit opportunities for children to engage in face-to-face social interactions, which are critical for developing communication skills. This explains that when young children spend too much exposure to the media, it can make them more distant from the real world because they might begin prioritizing virtual experiences over real ones.

In addition, Nabi and Wolfers (2022) examined the association between media exposure and emotional and behavioral problems. The study found that too much screen usage may cause problems with social interaction and emotional control. They highlighted the significance of balancing media use and in-person social interactions to reduce these negative impacts and encourage healthy emotional development. Hence, media exposure leads to drawbacks in the emotional behaviors of a child (Genelza, 2024).

Thus, excessive screen time for young children greatly impacts child development, including social skills development and emotional regulation. Addressing this issue is crucial, as too much exposure to media can hinder children's overall growth. Hence, this helps young children by fostering well-rounded social and emotional development.

Distorting Reality Perception and Weakening Attention Span through Media Sensationalism

The fourth theme produced during the data gathering is that media exposure to young children can alter how they perceive the real world. This represented that the media can contain exaggerated and biased content distracting children from the real world. Content creators' techniques to keep viewers interested through sensationalized media, like fast-paced TV series or videos, eye-catching images, rapid cuts, and overstimulating information, lead young children to be addicted and have a shorter attention span at an early age.

Also, Al-Ali et al. (2018) Evaluated parents' perspectives on how violent media affects children's aggressive behavior. Jordanian parents' knowledge and opinions regarding media's impact on children were recorded in this study. A large number of parents thought that their kids' increased aggression and behavioral problems were caused by their exposure to violent media. Parents conveyed worries about how such material would affect their kids' behavior in the long run.

On top of that, the findings of Gabrielle McHarg et al. (2020) support a rising body of research on links between toddler executive function (EF) and screen-based digital media exposure. The possible negative impacts of increased digital media exposure in toddlerhood on cognitive development were highlighted. Kids who spend more time on screens experience delays in critical executive function abilities like memory, problem-solving, and shorter attention spans.

Therefore, the way the world is portrayed through the media has a big impact on how kids view the world. Children exposed to sensationalized or exaggerated content may grow up with a distorted perception of the world, frequently seeing it as more hostile or dangerous than it is. The overstimulation from the fast-paced contents of media can lead to the shortening of attention span in children. This eventually leads to problems in their daily lives and difficulties in other aspects of life that call for concentration and focus.

Table 1: List of Literature on the Drawbacks of Media Exposure to Young Children

Authors	Title of the Study	Locale	Method	Results and Discussion	Recommendations	Themes
Pablo E. Brockmann, Blanca Diaz, Felipe Damiani, Luis Villarroel, Felipe Núñez, & Oliviero Bruni (2015)	Impact of Television on the Quality of sleep-in Preschool Children	Chile, South America	Quantitative	The study showed that having a TV set in the child's bedroom and being exposed to more hours of TV were connected with a significant decrease in young children's sleep quality. The exposure to TV had a significant impact on sleep terrors, nightmares, sleep talking, and	Parents should have control over and restrictions on the TV programs that their children watch. Poor parental limit setting may lead to excessive TV and electronic media exposure and irregular sleep habits.	Having Poor Sleeping Habits

				weariness upon awakening.	
Dinesh Kaimal, Ravi Teja Sajja, & Farzan Sasangohar (2017)	Investigating the Effects of Social Media Usage on Sleep Quality	Texas	Quantitative	Findings indicate a possible correlation between social media use and sleep quality. The study's results do not statistically support the theory that using social media before bed directly impacts sleep quality. However, the data does show a between social media consumption and sleep quality.	The use of specialized subjects and adjustment for normal stress and mood fluctuations that may potentially impact sleep quality is recommended to isolate social media's impact.
Bozhi Chen, Rob M. van Dam, Chuen Seng Tan, Hwee Ling Chua, Pey Gein Wong, Jonathan Y. Bernard, & Falk Müller-Riemenschneider (2019)	Screen viewing behavior and sleep duration among children aged two and below	Singapore	Quantitative	Researchers discovered that long screen exposure is associated with shorter sleep duration in children aged two and under. Children aged 6 months and under showed stronger associations than children aged 7 to 24 months.	Collaboration among caregivers, teachers, and healthcare professionals is crucial to reducing screen device use among young children. Nevertheless, further research is needed to confirm their observations and to develop effective intervention strategies for reducing SV among young children.
Aiman El Asam, Mythanna Samara, & Philip Terry (2019)	Problematic internet use and mental health among British children and adolescents	United Kingdom	Quantitative	The results showed that 1,814 young participants from UK schools' Problematic Internet Use (PIU) test results showed that males were more likely to score higher than females. That meant children's negligence and	There is an urgent need to develop intervention strategies to address this problem. Everyone must remember that the internet is a medium that needs to be utilized correctly.

				obsession with the internet resulted in negative impacts on daily routines, such as eating and sleeping habits, and psychosomatic issues.	
Betul Keles, Niall McCrae & Annmarie Grealish (2020)	A systematic review: the influence of social media on depression, anxiety and psychological distress in adolescents	London, United Kingdom	Qualitative	Throughout the 13 investigations, depression was often the measured outcome of exposure to media. Time spent on social media and addictive or problematic use were the main risk factors for depression, anxiety, and psychological distress that emerged from this review.	It is crucial to differentiate between the terms used for the relationship between social media use and mental health issues, and it is fair to say that there is an 'association' between the two. Correlations should be examined by objective researchers instead of embracing socially assumed truths.
Yumin Lin, Xueqin Zhang, Yinying Huang, Zhiwei Jia, Jing Chen, Wanling Hou, Lili Zhao, Guiyan Wang & Jiemin Zhu (2022)	Relationships between screen viewing and sleep quality for infants and toddlers in China: A cross-sectional study	China	Quantitative	This study showed that most toddlers in mainland China did not meet the World Health Organization's (WHO) screen time guidelines. Infants and toddlers who spent more time on screens slept less overall and at night—excessive TV viewing time negatively correlated with newborns' total sleep time.	To improve young children's sleep quality and promote their development, education programs on children's screen viewing, providing other educational materials instead of screening, more outdoor exercises and indoor parent-child activities, early sleep, restricting TV and smartphone use, and screen co-viewing are required.

Çağla ÖZDEMİR & Süleyman KELEŞ (2023)	The Relationship of Screen Exposure with Sleep Quality and Self-Regulation Skills in Preschool Children	Turkey	Quantitative	Findings show that excessive screen time in preschool children has been linked to sleep issues and poor self-regulation, including delayed speech development, a lack of physical activity, obesity, attention deficit, hyperactivity, and decreased cognitive capabilities.	Following the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) guideline, screen time should be reduced to about 1 hour per weekday and 3 hours on the weekends for children aged 2-5 years. We must limit their screen time so that their self-regulation abilities and sleeping habits will improve.	
Doreswamy Chandranaik, Jagdish Prasad Goyal, Kuldeep Singh, & Prawin Kumar (2024)	Association of digital media use with sleep habits in school children: A cross-sectional study	India	Quantitative	The study found that most children have poor sleeping habits, with prevalent digital media use. Approximately half of the children surveyed use digital media for at least 2 hours daily. In addition, using digital media 30 minutes before sleep is associated with poor sleep habits.	Public awareness of the effects of excessive digital media use in school is the need of the hour. The duration of safe digital media use for children is still debatable. However, the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) recommends less than 1-2 hours per day of media use in children.	
Katherine G. Hanson (2017)	The Influence of Early Media Exposure on Children's Development and Learning	USA	Quantitative	It was found that co-viewing television during infancy negatively impacted children's executive function skills and academic achievement into middle childhood. Children who co-viewed with their parents during infancy were	Parents must do three main ways to regulate their children: restricted mediation, active mediation, and co-viewing. Nathanson (2001) also found that different tactics for controlling children's television intake	Dealing with Aggressive Behaviors and Social Isolation

				likelier to exhibit poorer working memory, academic performance, and language skills.	led to diverse outcomes.
Rafi Antar (2019)	Exploring the Use of Electronic Media in Young Children's Lives and its Effects on Brain Development	Finland	Qualitative	The findings of this study demonstrate that exposure to electronic media changes multiple brain regions, which impacts children's behavioral, cognitive, and socio-affective development. Children's electronic media usage is still debatable despite its obvious impact on brain development.	All of us are exposed to electronic media, which has become an everyday necessity. However, many of us are unaware of how media can affect us when overused. We must have time to reflect on ourselves and engage in more manual activities rather than doing everything online.
Franzina Coutinho, Gauri Saxena, Akansha Shah, Shantanu Tilak, Neelu Desai, & Vrajesh Udani (2020)	Mobile media exposure and use in children aged zero to five years with diagnosed neurodevelopmental disability	Mumbai, India	Quantitative	Examined how children with neurodevelopmental diagnoses had been exposed to and had access to mobile media devices. It was also observed that social isolation caused these youngsters to rely on screens to make up for the lack of connection in their lives.	Clinicians and other caregivers must teach children how to use media responsibly and healthfully. This involves establishing appropriate limits, regulating usage, and offering useful examples of media-based interaction and communication.
Fatima Shirly Anitha, Udayakumar Narasimhan, Abhinayaa Janakiraman, Nivetha Janakarajan, & Priyadharshini Tamilselvan (2021)	Association of digital media exposure and addiction with child development and behavior: A cross-sectional study	India	Quantitative	The study analyzed 348 children aged 1½ to 5 years and 265 beyond 5 and 12 years. No differences were found in behavioral problems or screen media	Pediatricians must investigate children's media consumption during regular visits because it has consequences for their development and behavior. Given that there are no

				addiction based on gender or family type. Excessive screen time led to parental concerns in communication, problem-solving, and personal-social development.	Indian recommendations on media use for children, officials should create rules on healthy screen exposure based on more research to enhance digital literacy safely.
Sudheer Kumar Muppalla, Sravya Vuppalapati, Apeksha Reddy Pulliahgaru, & Himabindu Sreenivasulu (2023)	Effects of Excessive Screen Time on Child Development: An Updated Review and Strategies for Management	India	Qualitative	Findings say that excessive screen media usage in children can positively and negatively impact children's development. Screens enhance education and learning. However, studies have shown excessive screen time can negatively affect development and academic outcomes.	Parents should set an example for young children by controlling their screen time. Caregivers, educators, and healthcare professionals should understand the risks of excessive screen usage and apply solutions to encourage healthy development in children, such as alternate activities that improve mental and social-emotional abilities.
Song Meixuan (2024)	Assessing the impact of social media exposure on children's cognition and social development	Singapore	Mixed Method	The study stated that the large quantity of information on social media can cause information overload in young children, limiting their creativity and critical thinking. Additionally, young children may exhibit aggressive tendencies and other forms of imitative behavior due to being influenced by	Research suggests that children's social media use should be carefully regulated regarding time and content to promote social and cognitive development. Through appropriate supervision, this ensures that social media becomes a support for young children's healthy development

				unsuitable content.	rather than a hindrance. They should also encourage the positive journey of young children's behavioral development.	
Yolanda (Linda) Reid Chassiakos, MD;Jenny Radesky, MD;Dimitri Christakis, MD;Megan A. Moreno, MD;Corinn Cross, MD;David Hill, MD;Nusheen Ameenuddin, MD;Jeffrey Hutchinson, MD;Alanna Levine, MD;Rhea Boyd, MD;Robert Mendelson, MD;Wendy Sue Swanson, MD (2016)	Children and Adolescents and Digital Media	America	Qualitative	Children and adolescents widely use both new and traditional digital media. Results show that exposure to inaccurate, inappropriate, or unsafe content has a higher incidence of obesity and depression; adverse effects on sleep, attention, and learning are just a few of the negative outcomes and health concerns that have been linked to the content of media.	Promote health and wellness in children, emphasizing the value of maintaining a nutritious diet, regular exercise, proper sleep hygiene, and a supportive social environment.	Interfering with Social Skills Development and Emotional Regulation
Martina Cernik ov, David Smahel & Michelle F. Wright (2017)	Children's Experiences and Awareness of the Impact of Digital Media on Health	Czech Republic	Qualitative	Findings show that children who use technology have various eye problems, including eyestrain, red eyes, and eye pain. Children in this study also reported experiencing health issues such as headaches, eye problems, fatigue, and eating disorders as a result of excessively using technology.	Kids should be critical of the news from the media about the effects of technology. By taking a more balanced perspective on the effects of technology on health, parents and educators may support these essential points of view.	
Artur Mazur, Margherita Caroli, Igor	Reviewing and addressing the link between mass	Europe	Qualitative	The relationship between social media and the	Societies and stakeholders must be aware of the	

<p>Radziewicz-Winnicki, Paulina Nowicka, Daniel Weghuber, David Neubauer, Łukasz Dembinski, Francis P. Crawley, Martin White, & Adamos Hadjipanayis (2017)</p>	<p>media and the increase in obesity among European children: The European Academy of Paediatrics (EAP) and The European Childhood Obesity Group (ECOG) consensus statement</p>			<p>increasing obesity in kids epidemic in Europe was examined in this study. It was found that parents and society needed a better knowledge of how social media affects eating patterns and that there was evidence of a strong correlation between childhood media exposure and obesity rates across European countries.</p>	<p>impact that mass media can have on children's excessive and unregulated exposure to media. Providing scientific data regarding the possible health risks associated with excessive or improper mass media exposure should also be a part of health protection programs.</p>	
<p>Candice Wolf, Seth Wolf, Miriam Weiss, & Gustavo Nino (2018)</p>	<p>Children's Environmental Health in the Digital Era: Understanding Early Screen Exposure as a Preventable Risk Factor for Obesity and Sleep Disorders</p>	<p>United States of America</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>The negative effects of the current culture of early screen exposure are numerous and must be addressed as technology continues to invade and dominate social interactions. In this study, it is shown that early screen exposure has been linked to negative health matters, especially higher levels of obesity.</p>	<p>Schools may get involved by assigning kids to turn off their technology one day a week. Parents must monitor and restrict their children's access to all forms of screens. While Physicians must enquire, educate, and assist families in developing media usage strategies.</p>	
<p>Hyoung Yoon Chang, Eun-Jin Park, Hee-Jeong Yoo, Jee won Lee, & Yunmi Shin (2017)</p>	<p>Electronic Media Exposure and Use among Toddlers</p>	<p>Republic of Korea</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>Most children in Korea live in home environments using digital devices, with TV and smartphones being the most popular. The study found that 39% of toddlers use TV daily, while 23.4% use smartphones</p>	<p>Reducing screen time during the weekend can be a crucial goal in mediation. Doctors and mental health professionals should educate parents about the influence of media exposure on their children and make them</p>	<p>Distorting Reality Perception and Weakening Attention Span through Media Sensationalism</p>

				for over an hour on weekends.	aware of its importance.
Nahla Mansour Al-Ali, Hadeel Said Yaghy, Khulood K. Shattnawi & Noha M. Al-Shdayfat (2018)	Parents' Knowledge and Beliefs about the Impact of Exposure to Media Violence on Children's Aggression	Ar-ramtha, Jordan	Quantitative	Evaluated parents' perspectives on how violent media affects kids' aggressive behavior. Jordanian parents' knowledge and opinions regarding media's impact on children were recorded in this study.	Increasing parents' awareness of evidence-based media programs may have a positive behavioral effect on kids. Parents must participate in an educational health promotion program that teaches them how to manage and limit their children's exposure to video games and television shows.
Gabrielle McHarg, Andrew D. Ribner, Rory T. Devine & Claire Hughes (2020)	Screen Time and Executive Function in Toddlerhood: A Longitudinal Study	Birmingham, United Kingdom	Quantitative	Findings support a rising body of research on links between toddler executive function (EF) and screen-based digital media exposure. The results highlighted the possible negative impacts of increased digital media exposure in toddlerhood on cognitive development.	In today's world, parents, guardians, and teachers should use care when exposing small infants to large quantities of screen time. Understanding digital media's impacts on cognition is vital to support those who care for children. Additionally, increased screen time is associated with increased sedentary behavior and obesity.
Elena Bozzala, Giulia Spina, Rino Agostiniani, Sarah Barni, Rocco Russo, Elena Scarpato, Antonio Di Mauro, Anotnella Vita Di Stefano, Cinthia Caruso,	The Use of Social Media in Children and Adolescents: Scoping Review on the Potential Risks	Italy	Qualitative	Children increasingly use social media, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, when some parents tend to let their children be on screen all the time.	Families should educate their children about the dangers and risks of having children online. Educated individuals, such as medical professionals,

<p>Giovanni Corsello, and Annamaria Staiano. (2022)</p>				<p>This study showed how social media is useful, but excessive or improper use may increase the risk of health issues.</p>	<p>must teach families how to handle social media. Specifically, pediatricians should include reminders of the impacts of children's excessive access to media during check-up visits.</p>	
<p>Regil Sriandila & Dadan Suryana (2023)</p>	<p>Childhood Exploring the Impact of Digital Devices on Social Development in Young Children</p>	<p>Indonesia</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>Researchers found that parents of young children often use their smartphones when their children are around. This results in children getting fatigued, dissatisfied, angry, and enraged. In addition, the study shows that frequent use of electronic devices can cause dependence, which can result in addictive patterns of behavior.</p>	<p>Parents should monitor smartphone usage to set a good example for their children. So that gadgets as technological advances can still be used, and their obsession will not interfere with young children's social development as social beings.</p>	

As stated in the literature above, there are numerous drawbacks to early media exposure to children, such as having poor sleeping habits. Firstly, the media is an open platform where everyone who has access to it can post appropriate and inappropriate content. Secondly, exposure to inappropriate media content can disrupt the children's sleeping cycle, causing an unhealthy sleeping habit. Lastly, the media can be addicting, especially to children who are still in their developmental stage. To address these issues, educators should promote proper handling and monitoring of children's media access, where families can identify their child's behavior and how to mitigate this pressing concern.

With this, professionals and those who influence children must ensure what is best for future generations, especially since we live in a world where technology is a staple. Raising awareness and being educated about this problem can improve our future societies. These factors clearly show the urge for us to spread awareness. Communities have been established where some are concerned with the negative effects of media exposure on young children. Furthermore, young children should be guided as the media is one of the main reasons for unusual experiences in children's lives.

CONCLUSION

Considering all the research studies and information examined in this review it demonstrates how much influence media use has on kids' development. Children can sometimes be exposed to inappropriate content because the media is an open platform, which can harm their overall well-being.

Additionally, children who are exposed to the media too much may experience sleep deprivation and find it hard to return to a normal sleep schedule. Moreover, children who consume too much media are more likely to encounter explicit violent and aggressive behaviors that are posted in the media, which children may be able to replicate in real life. Social isolation may deepen,

making it worse for them to approach and converse normally with the people around them. Thus, children or young learners who spend too much time on the screens may spend less and less time trying to create a conversation, which can significantly affect how the children develop social interaction skills (Genelza, 2022).

With this, children who spend too much time on the media suffer from way more than just psychological and physical health. Monitoring how much screen time children receive from the media can help them be more creative and develop their critical thinking. Children may become mindless consumers of the media rather than using their curiosity and creativity to learn new things and explore, which limits the growth and development of children. Children's academic performance may be affected in the long run if the child consumes too much unusual and inappropriate media content, which may deteriorate their independent thinking.

Furthermore, continuous and addictive media consumption can lead to a poor and unhealthy lifestyle, leading to a sedentary lifestyle, and this can also lead to the child having poor life decisions. Children who are addicted to the media are more likely to eat unhealthy junk foods and are more likely to be physically inactive, which increases the possibility of the child being obese and other health complications. In addition to hurting their physical health, children who spend too much time on the screens are more likely to be moodier and have mood swings and breakdowns, which further worsens mental health problems like depression, anxiety, etc.

Lastly, a huge portion of the media is not meant for children to see, which may negatively impact their development. The media can easily fool a child and be met with unrealistic expectations and unreasonable body perceptions. Thus, children's self-esteem can be affected, and they become more sensitive to public opinions when they get older, which can seriously affect their emotional health.

With all this, the media is a dangerous platform for children. They should not have access to the media at such an early age. As discussed above, the media can negatively affect the child's overall development, cognitive thinking, and health. The media may affect the children in the long run as the media can also affect the children's academic performance. Therefore, the media is not a platform for children, and children should not be exposed to it at an early age.

RECOMMENDATION

Media exposure to young children is concerning in today's digital age. Although children can learn from media, excessive exposure can have alarming consequences. Young children should engage more in non-screen activities, such as playing with friends and families, reading, writing, drawing, and much more, to embrace healthy cognitive and social development. This is essential for children to explore various aspects of life rather than being overly exposed to media. This exploration will be beneficial to their future decision-making.

Moreover, young children exposed to media nowadays do not have proper supervision from adults, leading to too much media exposure than the average. Schools and policymakers should promote global cooperation by establishing guidelines for balanced media use to support future generations. Through this, it could potentially create change in children's daily routines.

Finally, media exposure to young children leads to numerous drawbacks in their lives. However, it all starts with the parents. Adults are said to be the role models of children. Hence, parent's control and how parents monitor their children have a big influence on children's growth. The following are effective parenting techniques: setting a good example by limiting their own screen time, especially when the kids are around, limiting their children's screen time, spending much time exploring things with them, involving them in social events, and much more. Additionally, we can contribute to changing and improving the future by increasing people's awareness of this issue.

REFERENCES

1. Anderson, D. R., Huston, A. C., Schmitt, K. L., Linebarger, D. L., Wright, J. C., & Larson, R. (2001). Early childhood television viewing and adolescent behavior: The recontact study. *Monographs of the society for Research in Child Development*, i-154.
2. Antar, R. (2019). Exploring the use of electronic media in young children's lives and its effects on brain development. *Journal of Early Childhood Education Research*, 8(1), 59-73.
3. Anitha, F. S., Narasimhan, U., Janakiraman, A., Janakarajan, N., & Tamilselvan, P. (2021). Association of digital media exposure and addiction with child development and behavior: A cross-sectional study. *Industrial psychiatry journal*, 30(2), 265-271.
4. Al-Ali, N. M., Yaghy, H. S., Shattnawi, K. K., & Al-Shdayfat, N. M. (2018). Parents' knowledge and beliefs about the impact of exposure to media violence on children's aggression. *Issues in mental health nursing*, 39(7), 592-599.

5. Bandura, A., & Walters, R. H. (1977). *Social learning theory* (Vol. 1, pp. 141-154). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice hall.
6. Bozzola, E., Spina, G., Agostiniani, R., Barni, S., Russo, R., Scarpato, E., ... & Staiano, A. (2022). The use of social media in children and adolescents: Scoping review on the potential risks. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(16), 9960.
7. Brockmann, P. E., Diaz, B., Damiani, F., Villarroel, L., Núñez, F., & Bruni, O. (2016). Impact of television on the quality of sleep in preschool children. *Sleep medicine*, 20, 140-144.
8. Chen, B., van Dam, R. M., Tan, C. S., Chua, H. L., Wong, P. G., Bernard, J. Y., & Müller-Riemenschneider, F. (2019). Screen viewing behavior and sleep duration among children aged 2 and below. *BMC public health*, 19, 1-10.
9. Chandranaik, D., Goyal, J. P., Singh, K., & Kumar, P. (2024). Association of digital media use with sleep habits in school children: A cross-sectional study. *Sleep Medicine: X*, 8, 100117.
10. Coutinho, F., Saxena, G., Shah, A., Tilak, S., Desai, N., & Udani, V. (2022). Mobile media exposure and use in children aged zero to five years with diagnosed neurodevelopmental disability. *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology*, 17(6), 645-651.
11. Cernikova, M., Smahel, D., & Wright, M. F. (2018). Children's experiences and awareness about impact of digital media on health. *Health communication*, 33(6), 664-673.
12. Chang, H. Y., Park, E. J., Yoo, H. J., won Lee, J., & Shin, Y. (2018). Electronic media exposure and use among toddlers. *Psychiatry investigation*, 15(6), 568.
13. Dy, A. B. C., Dy, A. B. C., & Santos, S. K. (2023). Measuring effects of screen time on the development of children in the Philippines: a cross-sectional study. *BMC public health*, 23(1), 1261.
14. Dewey, A., & Drahota, A. (2016). Introduction to systematic reviews: online learning module Cochrane Training.
15. del Dujo, Á. G., Vlieghe, J., Muñoz-Rodríguez, J. M., & Martín-Lucas, J. (2021). Thinking of (the Theory of) Education from the Technology of our Time. *Teoría de la Educación, Revista Interuniversitaria*, 33(2), 5-26.
16. El Asam, A., Samara, M., & Terry, P. (2019). Problematic internet use and mental health among British children and adolescents. *Addictive behaviors*, 90, 428-436.
17. Genelza, G. G. (2024). Integrating Tiktok As An Academic Aid In The Student's Educational Journey. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 12(6), 605-614.
18. GENELZA, G. (2024). YouTube Kids: A Channel for English Language Acquisition.
19. Genelza, G. G. (2022). English Proficiency And Academic Achievement Of Junior High School Students At University Of Mindanao Tagum College. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 376-384.
20. Hanson, K. (2017). The influence of early media exposure on children's development and learning.
21. Kaimal, D., Sajja, R. T., & Sasangohar, F. (2017, September). Investigating the effects of social media usage on sleep quality. In *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting* (Vol. 61, No. 1, pp. 1327-1330). Sage CA: Los Angeles, CA: SAGE Publications.
22. Keles, B., McCrae, N., & Grealish, A. (2020). A systematic review: the influence of social media on depression, anxiety and psychological distress in adolescents. *International journal of adolescence and youth*, 25(1), 79-93.
23. Kim, S. K., Wi, D. S., & Kim, K. M. (2023). Effect of Media Exposure on Social Development in Children. *Global Pediatric Health*, 10, 2333794X231159224.
24. Lin, Y., Zhang, X., Huang, Y., Jia, Z., Chen, J., Hou, W., ... & Zhu, J. (2022). Relationships between screen viewing and sleep quality for infants and toddlers in China: A cross-sectional study. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*, 10, 987523.
25. Liu, W., Wu, X., Huang, K., Yan, S., Ma, L., Cao, H., ... & Tao, F. (2021). Early childhood screen time as a predictor of emotional and behavioral problems in children at 4 years: a birth cohort study in China. *Environmental health and preventive medicine*, 26, 1-9.
26. Muppalla, S. K., Vuppapapati, S., Pulliahgaru, A. R., Sreenivasulu, H., & kumar Muppalla, S. (2023). Effects of excessive screen time on child development: an updated review and strategies for management. *Cureus*, 15(6).
27. Mar, R. A., Tackett, J. L., & Moore, C. (2010). Exposure to media and theory-of-mind development in preschoolers. *Cognitive development*, 25(1), 69-78.
28. Meixuan, S. (2024). Assessing the impact of social media exposure on children's cognition and social development. *development*, 7(9), 156-161.
29. Mazur, A., Caroli, M., Radziewicz-Winnicki, I., Nowicka, P., Weghuber, D., Neubauer, D., ... & Hadjipanayis, A. (2018). Reviewing and addressing the link between mass media and the increase in obesity among European children: The European Academy of Paediatrics (EAP) and The European Childhood Obesity Group (ECOG) consensus statement. *Acta paediatrica*, 107(4), 568-576.
30. McHarg, G., Ribner, A. D., Devine, R. T., & Hughes, C. (2020). Screen time and executive function in toddlerhood: A longitudinal study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 570392.

31. Özdemir, Ç., & Keleş, S. (2023). The Relationship of Screen Exposure with Sleep Quality and Self-Regulation Skills in Preschool Children. *Turkish Journal of Pediatric Disease*, 17(4), 285-290.
32. Reid Chassiakos, Y. L., Radesky, J., Christakis, D., Moreno, M. A., Cross, C., Hill, D., ... & Swanson, W. S. (2016). Children and adolescents and digital media. *Pediatrics*, 138(5).
33. Sriandila, R., & Suryana, D. (2023). Exploring the Impact of Digital Devices on Social Development in Young Children. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 15(2), 2230-2239.
34. Wolf, C., Wolf, S., Weiss, M., & Nino, G. (2018). Children's environmental health in the digital era: Understanding early screen exposure as a preventable risk factor for obesity and sleep disorders. *Children*, 5(2), 31.